

Evaluation of energy flows in the district heating system in Velenje

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Motivation

Source: Revesz et al. (2020) Developing novel 5th generation district energy networks. *Energy* 201:117389

Understand **energy flows** in the district heating system

Estimate **heat flow losses**

Analyse the effects of different

temperature regimes

Evaluate

system improvements

System modelling

- Describing complex district heating networks with a 0-degree **reduced-order model**:
 - Steady state conditions \longrightarrow normal operation, slow (seasonal) changes
 - Node method:

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \dot{Q}_{IN} = \sum_{i=1}^k \dot{Q}_{OUT}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \dot{m}_{IN} = \sum_{i=1}^k \dot{m}_{OUT}$$

- Low data density & computational effort required

Analyses of the distribution network – heat flow loss

No. of non-insulated pipes
No. of insulated pipes

	Branch A	Branch B
No. of non-insulated pipes	41 (64%)	37 (69%)
No. of insulated pipes	23 (36%)	17 (31%)

Analyses of the distribution network – heat flow loss

Branch A

SUPPLY LINE

SUPPLY LINE

RETURN LINE

RETURN LINE

Analyses of the distribution network – heat flow loss

Branch B

SUPPLY LINE

SUPPLY LINE

RETURN LINE

RETURN LINE

Analyses of the distribution network – temperature regimes

- Lower temperature regimes in DH systems lead to a reduction in distribution inefficiencies due to lower thermal losses
- Lower temperatures in the system open possibilities for the use of:
 - **Novel technologies** in energy generation, distribution, and consumption
 - Integration of **renewable sources**

REGIME	Season	Supply T	Return T
HIGHER	Winter	140°C	70°C
	Summer	110°C	70°C
LOWER	Winter	120°C	70°C
	Summer	90°C	70°C

Source: KPV – supply temperatures in Velenje

Comparisons of different configurations – temperature sweep

BRANCH A – ORIGINAL CONFIGURATION
[WINTER REGIME]

BRANCH A – FULLY INSULATED CONFIGURATION
[WINTER REGIME]

REFERENCE

Comparisons of different configurations – effect of insulation

BRANCH A – WINTER REGIME

REFERENCE

Not fully insulated!

BRANCH A – SUMMER REGIME

Not fully insulated!

Comparisons of different configurations – effect of insulation

BRANCH B – WINTER REGIME

REFERENCE

Not fully insulated!

BRANCH B – SUMMER REGIME

Not fully insulated!

Comparisons of different configurations - summary

Branches A and B – annual values:

	BRANCH A	BRANCH B
Total energy supplied p.a. [MWh]	64699	69295
Reference: Original configuration Total energy losses p.a. [MWh]	4735	5866
Original configuration with lower temp. regimes (140->120 & 110->90) Total energy losses p.a. [MWh]	3870	4733
Difference relative to reference [MWh]	-866 (-18%)	-1133 (-19%)
CO ₂ reduction p.a. [t]	251	329
Fully insulated configuration with lower temp. regimes (140->120 & 110->90) Total energy losses p.a. [MWh]	1006	1154
Difference relative to reference [MWh]	-3729 (-79%)	- 4712 (-80%)
CO ₂ reduction p.a. [t]	1081	1366

Estimates of the whole DHS network

- Considers contributions from the supply, distribution, and the consumers:
 - **Supply:** Lower temperature regimes
 - **Distribution:** Insulation improvements assumed to be carried out only on the pipelines of the primary network; lower temperature regimes neglected in the secondary network
 - **Consumers:** Building stock savings are estimated to reach a maximum of 60% compared to the current state (corresponds with estimates in literature)

Estimates of the whole DHS network

- Information from branches A and B used to extend the ROM simulation tool
- Assuming the same conditions in the entire network
- Normalised heat flow loss $\Delta\dot{q}_L$ as a function of the pipe nominal diameter DN

WINTER REGIME

SUMMER REGIME

The effect of improved building stock quality

The location's building stock has an important impact on the overall efficiency of a DHS system:

- European Commission:

Poor energy performance of the building stock is an obstacle in reducing supply temperatures¹

- Commission's long-term decarbonisation goal:

55% reduction in heat demand in the building stock by 2050²

A system redesign should include a **forecast of expected heat demand** in Velenje:

- Analysis of 4 years of data (2016-2019) shows better energy performance even in partially renovated buildings → average improvement: **35%**
- Estimated efficiency improvement for fully renovated buildings: **30% - 60%**

¹Bacquet A. *et al.* (2021) Overview of District Heating and Cooling Markets and Regulatory Frameworks under the Revised Renewable Energy Directive. *European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy*

²Mathiesen B. *et al.* (2023) Heat Matters: The Missing Link in REPowerEU: 2030 District Heating Deployment for a long-term Fossil-free Future. *Alborg University*

The effect of improved building stock quality

- Estimates of lower energy needs in buildings: information about available building stock × possible savings in %:

$$\dot{Q}_{build_{LowCons}} = \dot{Q}_{build} r_{build}$$

Monthly average values (2020)

Heat flow source [MW]				
Month	TEŠ	C RTP	Velenje	Šoštanj
JAN	66.86	66.87	55.64	11.22
FEB	56.51	55.95	46.97	8.93
MAR	51.56	50.68	42.73	7.81
APR	31.83	31.28	26.12	5.05
MAY	21.50	21.68	17.93	3.62
JUN	16.28	15.88	13.21	2.87
JUL	13.44	13.35	11.13	2.33
AUG	12.74	12.73	10.57	2.16
SEP	15.68	15.75	10.98	2.39
OCT	34.95	35.38	29.36	5.81
NOV	52.70	53.57	35.78	20.39
DEC	65.16	66.69	52.76	12.44

Estimated savings of total heat flow in Velenje (incl. lower temp. regime)

BUILDING STOCK SAVINGS					
15% [MW]	20% [MW]	25% [MW]	30% [MW]	50% [MW]	60% [MW]
50.97	50.49	50.02	49.54	47.64	46.69
42.66	42.25	41.85	41.44	39.81	38.99
38.66	38.28	37.90	37.51	35.99	35.22
23.08	22.78	22.49	22.19	21.00	20.41
15.56	15.36	15.17	14.98	14.20	13.82
11.31	11.21	11.11	11.01	10.61	10.41
9.49	9.39	9.29	9.19	8.81	8.61
8.96	8.86	8.76	8.67	8.28	8.08
9.36	9.26	9.16	9.06	8.65	8.45
26.18	25.89	25.61	25.32	24.17	23.60
32.26	31.87	31.48	31.08	29.51	28.72
48.01	47.54	47.06	46.59	44.68	43.73

Estimates of annual heat flows in the Velenje DHS

(Estimates based on data for reference year 2020)

Conclusions & potential for future work

- Defossilisation of district heating systems is a Europe-wide endeavour
 - BUT:** difficult to standardise & compare
- Analyses of individual sections or branches of the network provide better references for comparisons
- Data in literature show similar trends for lower temperature regimes (e.g. Latvia, Graz)
- **Quality of insulation** in the distribution network and in the building stock have the biggest impact
- Further improvements to the system will require a *multi-level* & *multi-system* approach:
 - **Reduced-order modelling will be key** for future multi-system simulations

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